

Set deep learning for protocol generalisation in machine-learning-based brain microstructure estimation

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Impact

We show that set-deep-learning-based parameter estimation generalises across acquisition protocols, enabling fast, single-model microstructure mapping without retraining.

Synopsis

Motivation: Learning-based microstructure estimation often assumes fixed protocols, limiting translation and reuse.

Goals: Train once, deploy anywhere: estimate NODDI parameters robustly across variable-length, unseen protocols.

Approach: Treat voxel-level data as an unordered set and train PointNet to predict microstructure from data without assuming a fixed acquisition protocol.

Results: On unseen DSI and UKBB protocols, total MSE was lower than conventional fitting (DSI 0.02 vs 0.05 ; UKBB 0.03 vs 0.06). Map generation took under a minute versus hours.

Introduction

Diffusion MRI (dMRI) enables tissue microstructure measurements *in vivo*. Biophysical models provide interpretable parameters but conventional parameter estimation requires voxel-wise non-linear optimisation that is slow and noise-sensitive. Machine-learning (ML) approaches have been proposed to address these limitations¹. However, most learning-based parameter-estimation methods assume a fixed acquisition protocol and thus cannot be used on data acquired with different protocols. We propose a novel strategy, based on set deep learning (SDL), to tackle this problem. SDL is designed to work with data of variable sizes and no intrinsic ordering, characteristics shared by dMRI data. In particular, we demonstrate this approach with PointNet², a seminal model that learns from unstructured point clouds.

Problem statement

Volume i of dMRI scan is acquired with diffusion encoding (b_i, \mathbf{g}_i) , where $b_i \in \mathbb{R}_+$ is the b -value quantifying diffusion-weighting magnitude and $\mathbf{g}_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is a unit vector defining the diffusion encoding direction. Ignoring physical constants and using $\mathbf{q}_i = \sqrt{b_i} \mathbf{g}_i$, voxel-level data form a q -space³ point cloud: $\mathcal{D} = \{(\mathbf{q}_i, S_i)\}_{i=1}^N$, where S_i is the measured signal and N is the number of acquisitions. We denote the protocol by $\mathcal{Q} = \{\mathbf{q}_i\}$. This motivates learning formulations that treat dMRI data as an unordered set rather than as a fixed-length ordered vector.

A biophysical forward model f expresses the signal as $\hat{S}_i = f(\mathbf{q}_i, \boldsymbol{\theta})$, where \hat{S}_i is the predicted signal and $\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \Theta \subset \mathbb{R}^d$ are microstructural parameters, and Θ is the space of biologically plausible values. Conventional model fitting usually solves $\hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}} = \arg \min_{\boldsymbol{\theta} \in \Theta} \sum_{i=1}^N (S_i - \hat{S}_i)^2$. Maximum-likelihood estimators explicitly modelling Rician noise⁴ are conceptually similar.

Our learning problem is to find a map $F_\phi : \mathcal{D} \mapsto \hat{\boldsymbol{\theta}}$, where ϕ are learnable parameters, that produces accurate microstructural parameter estimates while accepting variable-length input data and generalising across protocols without retraining.

Methods

We evaluated if PointNet (Figure 1) could accurately estimate neurite orientation dispersion and density imaging (NODDI)⁵ parameters intra-neurite signal fraction (f_{ic}), orientation dispersion index (ODI), and isotropic signal fraction (f_{iso}), from real-world protocols not seen during training. The MATLAB NODDI toolbox⁶, widely used in neuroscience, was used as the state-of-the-art (SOTA) baseline.

Training

We simulated 10,000 voxels with $f_{ic}, \text{ODI}, f_{iso} \sim \mathcal{U}(0.025, 0.975)$ and random orientations. For domain generalisation, for each voxel, data was generated using 10 random protocols: 2–5 shells, $b \sim \mathcal{U}(0.25, 5)$ ms/ μm^2 , 12–128 directions per shell, and Rician noise with $\text{SNR} \sim \mathcal{U}(10, 40)$. The loss was mean squared error (MSE). The optimiser was Adam with a learning rate of 10^{-3} with 1% decay each fifth epoch. We trained for 500 epochs with batch size of 10 and gradient clipping with a max-norm of 1. At each voxel, a fraction of points $f \sim \mathcal{U}(0, 0.5)$ were dropped with probability 0.5.

Evaluation

We evaluated the network with two protocols unseen during training: Diffusion Spectrum Imaging (DSI) with 303 points and a maximum b -value of 5 ms/ μm^2 ⁷, and the 2-shell UK Biobank (UKBB) protocol with non-zero b -values of 1 and 2 ms/ μm^2 with 50 directions each⁸. Data was simulated on a grid covering the parameter space: 0.1, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.9 for each parameter. We created 100 Rician noise realisations per voxel with signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of 30 for DSI and 20 for UKBB.

Results

Accuracy

On the test dataset, the model reduced total MSE compared to conventional fitting for both DSI (0.02 vs 0.05) and UKBB (0.03 vs 0.06). The errors across parameter space are shown in [Figure 2](#) and the MSEs per parameter are reported in the table in [Figure 3](#).

Qualitative maps

Microstructural maps produced by the trained model are shown in [Figure 4](#). On a laptop with Intel Core i7-13700H \times 20 and NVIDIA RTX A1000 6GB Laptop GPU, PointNet generated maps in less than a minute, compared to up to six hours it took with the toolbox. The maps exhibit realistic spatial structure and anatomical plausibility, but show different contrast due to the biophysical model's protocol-dependent biases and the fact that the model was trained on data that does not fully capture real data (e.g., simplified orientation distribution). These results are presented for qualitative illustration of the potential of a single model applied to variable data. Model-dependent biases are outside our scope and future research may focus on replicating toolbox performance using self-supervised learning ⁹.

Conclusion

We have shown that a permutation-invariant deep learning model can be trained once on randomised simulated data and then deployed across diverse, unseen dMRI acquisitions protocols for accurate microstructural parameter mapping, rivalling SOTA methods.

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Figures and Tables

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Figure 2: NODDI parameter estimation errors for DSI (a) and UKBB (b) protocols on the test dataset.

DSI

	PointNet	Toolbox
f_{ic}	0.02	0.11
ODI	0.03	0.03
f_{iso}	0.01	0.01

UKBB

	PointNet	Toolbox
f_{ic}	0.03	0.13
ODI	0.04	0.04
f_{iso}	0.01	0.01

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Figure 3: Mean squared errors over the test dataset for DSI and UKBB protocols.

Figure 4: Axial slices of NODDI parameter maps produced by the trained model on DSI and UKBB protocols.